

POSSIBLE ANTIAMOEBCIC AGENTS. PART V. MANNICH BASES FROM SUBSTITUTED THIOCHROMANONES

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Mannich bases from several substituted thiochromanones have been prepared with a view to testing their antiamoebic activity.

The Mannich base hydrochlorides of a number of thiochromanones, prepared in this laboratory (Sen and Kulkarni, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 687), have been found to possess appreciable *in vitro* antiamoebic activity. With a view to studying the effect of introduction of different substituents in the thiochromanone nucleus and the basic side-chain on the antiamoebic activity, a number of Mannich base hydrochlorides (I) have now been prepared from four substituted (6- & 8-methoxy, 8-methyl & 8-ethyl) thiochromanones.

[R' & R'' = substituents in the basic side chain.

R₁ & R₂ = substituents in the thiochromanone nucleus].

The thiochromanones were obtained by the cyclisation of the appropriate thiophenoxypropionic acids and were characterised through their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

The required β -thiophenoxypropionic acids were prepared by the condensation of the appropriate thiophenols, viz., 2-methoxy-, 4-methoxy-, 2-ethyl- and 2-methyl-, with β -propiolactone according to Gresham *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 661).

The required thiophenols were obtained by following the method of Tarbell *et al.* ("Org. Syn." Col. Vol. III, p. 809) using the condensation of the appropriate diazonium salts with potassium ethylxanthate, followed by hydrolysis of the resulting xanthogenic esters.

β -(2-Methyl- and 2-ethyl-thiophenoxy)-propionic acids underwent cyclisation with concentrated sulphuric acid (98%) (Hurd *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 5065) but the β -(2-methoxy- and 4-methoxy-thiophenoxy)-propionic acids could only be cyclised by distilling the thiophenoxypropionic acid with P₂O₅ under reduced pressure (Krollpfeiffer *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1925, 58, 1654).

The Mannich base hydrochlorides (I) of these thiochromanones were prepared by taking equimolar quantities of a thiochromanone, paraformaldehyde and a primary or a secondary amine hydrochloride in dry benzene and refluxing on the water-bath for 3 to 6 hours. The reaction mixture was acidified at the start of the reaction either by the addition of a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid or where this method did not succeed, dry HCl gas was passed. In all the cases, the Mannich base hydrochlorides separated as fine crystalline solids during the reaction and were isolated by filtration on the pump. These were recrystallised from absolute ethyl-alcohol.

Most of the Mannich base hydrochlorides are soluble in water. In some cases the aqueous solution, when allowed to stand at room temperature, became turbid and deposited a sticky substance indicating decomposition, while in others, where the solutions were stable, the original compounds were recovered back on evaporation.

The Mannich base hydrochlorides were characterised through their picrates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Substituted Thiophenols.—*o*-Methyl-, *o*-ethyl-, *o*-methoxy- and *p*-methoxy- thiophenols were prepared from the corresponding anilines according to Tarbell *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

β -Propiolactone was obtained from Eastman Kodak Ltd.

Substituted β -thiophenoxypropionic acids were obtained from the above thiophenols by condensing them with β -propiolactone in alkaline medium according to Gresham *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

Of the four β -thiophenoxypropionic acids, two are known; β -2-methyl- and β -4-methoxy-thiophenoxypropionic acids have been reported by Hurd *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) and Krollpfeiffer *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) respectively. β -2-Ethyl- and β -2-methoxy-thiophenoxypropionic acids have been prepared for the first time.

The m.p., yields, neutralisation equivalents and the analytical data of the two new thiophenoxypropionic acids are recorded below.

TABLE I

β -Thiophenoxy-propionic acid.	M. P.	Yield.	Neut. equiv.		%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
β -2-Ethyl-	53°	80%	209.6	210	62.60	62.85	6.80	6.66
β -2-Methoxy-	89°	65	212.3	212	56.30	56.60	5.40	5.66

Substituted Thiochromanones: 8-Methyl- and 8-ethyl-thiochromanones were obtained by the cyclisation of the corresponding β -thiophenoxypropionic acids with H₂SO₄ (conc., 98%). In both the cases the thiophenoxy acids were treated with 10

parts of ice-cold H_2SO_4 (conc.) when a deep red solution was obtained which was allowed to stand at room temperature for 5 hours and stirred occasionally. On pouring over crushed ice the thiochromanone separated out which was filtered and purified in the usual way (Hurd *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

8- & 6-Methoxythiochromanones.—These were obtained by the cyclisation of the corresponding β -thiophenoxypropionic acids with P_2O_5 , as described by Krollpfeiffer *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). The acids were distilled under reduced pressure with 2 parts of P_2O_5 , when the thiochromanones were obtained in the distillate and were characterised through their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

Of these, 8-methylthiochromanone has been reported by Hurd *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) and 6-methoxythiochromanone by Krollpfeiffer *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). The m.p., yields, and the analytical data of the two thiochromanones and of their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones, which are new, are recorded below.

TABLE II

Substituted thiochromanones.	M.P.	Yield.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.		2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones.		
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	M. P.	%Nitrogen.	
								Found.	Calc.
8-Ethyl.	37°	55.5%	68.50	68.74	6.40	6.25	190°	15.00	15.06
8-Methoxy.	98°	68.7	61.80	61.85	4.90	5.15	233°	14.80	14.98

Mannich base hydrochlorides from substituted thiochromanones were obtained as follows: A mixture of thiochromanone (0.01 M) and paraformaldehyde (0.01 M) was taken in dry benzene (25 c.c.) in a flask and refluxed for about 30 minutes. To this was added the primary or secondary amine hydrochloride (0.01 M) and refluxed for 10 minutes. It was then acidified either with 5-10 drops of HCl (conc., A. R.) (A) or by passing dry HCl gas (B) and refluxed again for 3 to 6 hours, during which the Mannich base hydrochloride separated as a fine crystalline mass. After the completion of the reaction, the mixture was cooled and the crystalline mass filtered at the pump, washed with dry benzene and finally recrystallised from absolute ethyl alcohol.

The Mannich base hydrochlorides are soluble either in cold or hot water (excepting number 1, 4 and 11, Table II). All the Mannich base hydrochlorides gave intense bright red or reddish violet colour with a drop of H_2SO_4 (conc.). The Mannich base hydrochlorides were characterised through their picrates.

Picrates.—The Mannich base hydrochloride (I) (0.05 g.) was dissolved in 5 c.c. of hot water and mixed with 5 c.c. of a saturated aqueous picric acid solution, and boiled; on cooling, the crystalline picrate separated out, which was filtered and then recrystallised from ethyl alcohol.

TABLE III
(Vide structure I)

No.	R' & R''	Acidification medium	M. P.	Yield, %	Mol. formula.	%Nitrogen.		M. P.	Mol. formula.	%Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.
R ₁ & R ₂ = 8-methyl.											
1.	Benzyl-	(B)	180°	34%	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ ONCIS	4.53	4.20				
2.	Morpholinyl-	"	164°	30	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₂ NCIS	4.30	4.46				
3.	Dimethyl-	"	162-63°	68	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ ONCIS	5.00	5.16	150°	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	11.95	12.10
R ₁ & R ₂ = 8-ethyl.											
4.	Benzyl-	(A) ₁	157-58°	35	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ ONCIS	3.96	4.03				
5.	Morpholinyl-	"	158-59°	50	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₂ NCIS	4.50	4.27	163°	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.30	10.70
6.	Dimethyl-	(B)	164-65°	68	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ ONCIS	5.00	4.90	140°	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	11.90	11.70
7.	Piperidyl-	(B)	173°	30	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ ONCIS	4.50	4.30	152°	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.55	10.80
R ₁ & R ₂ = 8-methoxy.											
8.	Dimethyl-	"	184-85°	50	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₂ NCIS	4.50	4.87	154°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	11.40	11.60
9.	Piperidyl-	"	154°	25	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ NCIS	4.10	4.27				
10.	Morpholinyl-	"	153-54°	30	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₂ NCIS	4.35	4.25				
R ₁ & R ₂ = 6-methoxy.											
11.	Benzyl-	(B)	167°	40	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₂ NCIS	4.00	4.01				
12.	Piperidyl-	"	235°	25	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ NCIS	4.30	4.27				

Test for Stability.—The compounds (6, 5, 8, 3 and 11 of Table III) (0.05 g. each) were dissolved in 5 c.c. of water separately and then allowed to stand at room temperature for 24 hours. Solutions of No. 5, 8, 6 and 3 became turbid and deposited a sticky residue showing decomposition, whereas in case of No. 11, the original compound was recovered back on evaporation.

The melting points, yields, and analyses of the Mannich base hydrochlorides and their picrates are shown in Table III.

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